

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice on Dengue among Patients and Bystanders Attending General Medicine OPD in a Tertiary Care Hospital, Puducherry

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Abstract:

Background: Dengue is the most widespread vector-borne infectious disease of humans. Over half of the world's population now live in tropical and subtropical zones that place them at risk of infection.

Objectives: To assess the level of knowledge and attitude about the cause of dengue, its spread and symptoms. Also, to assess the practices related to prevention of dengue and its complications.

Methods: This was a cross-sectional study carried out in the Department of General Medicine for a period of 3 months. Both patients and bystanders who were aged more than 18 years, attending the OPD during the study period and gave informed consent were the study participants. The sample size was estimated to be 356. The data was collected using a semi structured questionnaire. Statistical analysis was done using descriptive statistics.

Results: 31.4% were found to have good knowledge and 48.3% moderate knowledge. 95.6% thought dengue to be transmitted through mosquito and 84.3% had answered its common symptoms. 97.6% thought dengue to be a serious illness, and 96.3% reported it will be possible to control mosquitos. 89.9% reported to use mosquito control aids, 81.5% reported that they covered drinking water container, and 70.3% reported that they kept themselves hydrated during the illness.

Conclusion: Many had good knowledge and the attitude pattern was also positive among the participants. Certain practices like source reduction activities and wearing full sleeve clothing have to be encouraged among the study population.

Keywords: Dengue, Knowledge, Attitude, Practice, Dengue shock syndrome, Dengue haemorrhagic fever, Aedes.

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Introduction

Dengue is an acute systemic viral infection that gets transmitted between humans by means of Aedes mosquito. The disease has over time evolved from sporadic to major public health problem [1]. Estimates had reported dengue to cause 50 to 100 million cases of dengue fever, 50,000 cases of dengue haemorrhagic fever and 24,000 deaths worldwide every year [2,3].

Dengue at present is having both endemic and epidemic transmission cycles [1,4]. The clinical manifestations of dengue involve a wide spectrum – varying from mild fever to dengue shock syndrome. The latter end is a life-threatening condition. Following infection, a lifelong immunity

is developed in dengue and the immunity is type specific. It was also reported that the serious infection was found to be due to secondary infection with heterologous type in most of the cases [5,6]. The disease with its increased geographical extension, magnitude of the cases and the disease severity has resulted in substantial social and economic effect [7].

In order to prevent dengue, the core strategies include vector control and surveillance. The disease per se has no specific treatment⁸. In order to implement the vector control measures effectively there shall be support, cooperation and participation from the community [9]. Knowing the

baseline knowledge, attitude and practice regarding dengue is of paramount importance as it will aid in creating future interventions aiming at educating the people regarding vector control and promoting practices that prevent considerable morbidity due to the disease. Studies had reported a positive correlation between knowledge, attitude and practice towards dengue its prevention and control [10,11].

Despite the widespread prevalence of dengue and the burden it causes cyclically, not many studies had reported on the level of knowledge, attitude and practice towards dengue and its prevention among the general population [12]. The present study was carried out with the objective of assessing the level of knowledge and attitude about the cause of dengue, its spread and symptoms and the other objective was to assess the practice about prevention of dengue and its complications.

Material and methods

This was a cross-sectional study carried out in the Department of General Medicine, Sri Venkateshwaraa Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Puducherry, India. The study was carried out for a period of 3 months between September 2023 and November 2023. Ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee. Both patients and bystanders aged more than 18 years and who had attended the out-patient department during the study period were included into the study. Informed consent was obtained from all the participants.

The sample size for the study was determined using the Open Epi Software v3.01. The confidence interval was kept at 95%, and the margin of error at 0.5%. The expected frequency was 69.6% [13]. The sample size was calculated to be 356. Convenient sampling was followed.

The data for the study was collected using a validated and pretested, semi structured questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of four parts. Part I dealt with sociodemographic variables. The sociodemographic variables included in the study were age, sex, place of residence, education, monthly income, and employment status.

The knowledge part consisted of 10 questions. The correct answer was scored one and wrong answer was scored zero. The minimum obtainable knowledge score will be zero while maximum will be 10. Anyone who scores 4 or less were categorized as poor knowledge while score between 5 to 7 were categorized as moderate knowledge and a score of more than 7 was categorized as good knowledge.

The attitude part consisted of 10 attitude related questions and the practice part consisted of 10 practice related questions. Most of the attitude and

practice questions were provided with yes or no type of answers. The data collected were entered into Microsoft Excel v2019 and the master chart was created. The master chart was then loaded onto SPSS v26 for statistical analysis.

Descriptive statistics were used in analysis of the data. The qualitative variables were expressed using frequency and percentage. Bar charts and pie diagrams were used to represent the data pictographically.

Results

Out of 356 participants, 109 (30.6%) participants were in the age group 51 to 60 years followed by 98 (27.5%) were in the age group 41 to 50 years. 208 (58.4%) were males. 219 (61.5%) resided in rural area. 97 (27.2%) studied up to middle school followed by 63 (17.7%) up to primary school and 61 (17.1%) were illiterate. 117 (32.8%) were earning between 10,001 to 25000 rupees followed by 89 (25%) earning between 5,001 to 10,000 rupees. 83 (23.3%) were earning less than 5000 rupees. 228 (64.1%) were employed.

Knowledge Scores:

With regard to knowledge, 257 (72.3%) reported correctly that Dengue is a viral infection. 340 (95.6%) reported Dengue to be transmitted through mosquito. 182 (51.1%) answered that the dengue mosquito bites at the daytime and 213 (59.8%) correctly reported the breeding place of the Aedes mosquito.

147 (41.3%) had known that Dengue does not transmit through direct contact. 300 (84.3%) correctly stated fever and joint pain to be the common symptoms of dengue. 280 (78.6%) had stated that the complications of dengue could lead to death. 151 (42.4%) had known about dengue through newspaper followed by 86 (24.2%) through social media. 227 (63.9%) correctly answered dengue to be more prevalent during the rainy season (Table 2). 112 (31.4%) were found to have good knowledge about dengue followed by 172 (48.3%) with moderate knowledge. 72 (20.3%) were found to have poor knowledge (Fig 2).

Attitude Scores:

With regard to attitude, 347 (97.6%) thought dengue to be serious illness. 156 (43.7%) had experienced dengue. 197 (55.4%) reported that there was no cure to dengue. 262 (73.5%) reported that drinking plenty of water and taking adequate rest is beneficial in dengue.

278 (78.2%) thought drinking papaya juice is beneficial in dengue. 343 (76.3%) reported that it is possible to control mosquito. 279 (78.3%) reported that they will seek medical care if they suspect dengue. 215 (60.3%) reported that dengue reinfection is possible among previously infected

persons. 334 (93.8%) were of attitude that people shall actively take part in controlling vectors of mosquito borne diseases. 153 (43%) were of attitude that management of mosquito prevention and control is the responsibility of both government and the people (Table 3).

Practice scores:

With regard to practice towards dengue, 290 (81.5%) reported that they use to cover drinking water container in home. 187 (52.4%) reported to use mosquito nets to cover windows and doors. 320 (89.9%) reported to use mosquito control aids to control mosquito. 219 (61.5%) reported to turn containers upside down to prevent water collection

in and around home. 183 (51.4%) reported to cut bushes and clean surroundings regularly. 155 (43.4%) reported to wear long dresses and full sleeves to prevent mosquito bites.

117 (32.9%) reported to have taken part in dengue related campaigns. 171 (48.1%) reported to have donated blood for dengue patient. 230 (64.5%) reported to have done pest control measures recently and 250(70.3%) reported to have kept themselves hydrated during illness (Table 4).

142 (44.4%) reported to use mosquito repellets followed by 98 (30.6%) reported to use mosquito nets and 54 (16.9%) reported to use sprays (Fig 2).

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics among the study participants

Variables		Frequency (n=356)	Percentage (%)
Age group (in years)	18-30	32	8.9
	31-40	54	15.2
	41-50	98	27.5
	51-60	109	30.6
	>60	63	17.7
Sex	Male	208	58.4
	Female	148	41.6
Place of residence	Urban	137	38.5
	Rural	219	61.5
Education	Illiterate	61	17.1
	Primary	63	17.7
	Middle	97	27.2
	Secondary	54	15.2
	Higher secondary	31	8.7
	Graduate and above	50	14.1
Monthly income (in rupees)	<5000	83	23.3
	5,001-10,000	89	25.0
	10,001-25,000	117	32.8
	25,001-50,000	43	12.1
	>50,000	24	6.7
Employment status	Employed	228	64.1
	Unemployed	128	35.9

Table 2: Distribution according to correct answer to the knowledge-based questions

S.No	Question	Correct answer	N=356	%
K1	What type of infection is dengue?	Viral	257	72.3
K2	Is Dengue transmitted through mosquito	Yes	340	95.6
K3	Time at which dengue mosquito bites	Day time	182	51.1
K4	Place at which the dengue mosquito breed	Flowerpot	213	59.8
K5	Can dengue be transmitted by direct contact with another person?	No	147	41.3
K6	What are the common symptoms of dengue?	Fever with joint pain	300	84.3
K7	What are the complications of dengue?	Low platelet	189	53
K8	Dengue complication leads to death	Yes	280	78.6
K9	How do you know about dengue?	Newspaper	151	42.4
		Social media	86	24.2
		Pamphlets	51	14.3
		Dengue campaign	68	19.1
K10	Dengue is more prevalent in this season of the year	Rainy season	227	63.9

Figure 1: Pattern of knowledge regarding dengue among the participants

Table 3: Distribution according to attitude towards dengue among the participants

S.No	Question	N=356	%	
A1	Dengue is a serious illness	347	97.6	
A2	I have experienced dengue	156	43.7	
A3	There is no cure for dengue	197	55.4	
A4	Drinking plenty of water and taking adequate rest is beneficial in Dengue	262	73.5	
A5	Drinking papaya juice is beneficial in dengue	278	78.2	
A6	It is possible to control mosquito	343	96.3	
A7	I will seek medical care immediately if I suspect dengue	279	78.3	
A8	Reinfection can occur in previously infected persons	215	60.3	
A9	People should actively take part in controlling vectors of mosquito borne diseases	334	93.8	
A10	Responsible for management of mosquito prevention and control	Myself	56	15.7
		Government	110	30.9
		Both	153	43

Table 4: Distribution according to practice towards dengue among the participants

S.No	Question	N=356	%
P1	We use to cover drinking water container in home	290	81.5
P2	We use mosquito nets to cover windows and doors	187	52.4
P3	We use mosquito control aids to control mosquito	320	89.9
P4	We turn containers upside down to prevent water collection in and around the home	219	61.5
P5	We frequently cut bushes and clean surroundings regularly	183	51.4
P6	We wear long dresses and full sleeves to prevent mosquito bites	155	43.4
P7	I have taken part in dengue campaign	117	32.9
P8	I have donated blood for a dengue patient	171	48.1
P9	We have done pest control measures recently	230	64.5
P10	I have kept myself hydrated during illness	250	70.3

Figure 2: Distribution according to control aids used

Discussion

Dengue is an acute systemic viral infection that has been infecting millions of people globally every year and responsible for thousands of deaths. The vector for the virus is *Aedes mosquito* [1,2,3]. In order to prevent the spread of infection vector control is important and also in case if the infection occurs seeking medical care early and adequate hydration are vital to prevent the mortality and morbidity. In order to achieve the above having adequate knowledge regarding dengue its transmission and methods to prevent is vital. Not only knowledge, a good attitude and sufficient practice is also important in order to fight the infection [11].

The present study was cross sectional study done for a period of 3 months with objective of assessing the level of knowledge and attitude about the cause of dengue, its spread and symptoms and the other objective was to assess the practice about prevention of dengue and its complications. Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional ethics committee and the sample size was calculated to be 356. Informed consent was obtained from all the participants included the study.

In the present study, 31.4% were found to have good knowledge about dengue followed by 48.3% with moderate knowledge. A study by Harapan H et al. reported 40% to have good knowledge about dengue [14]. Almost 95% participants reported dengue to be transmitted through mosquito. Kumaran E et al. reported a similar proportion among their study participants to report the same. Only 51.1% reported the mosquito biting time correctly which is lesser than the percentage

reported by Kumaran E et al [15]. With regard to the symptoms of dengue, Itrat A et al. also reported almost 80% percentage to state fever as the common symptom which was similar to the present study [12]. The present study found mass media as the frequent source of information about dengue and similar result was also reported by Harapan H et al [14]. The study population has considerable knowledge with regard to the infection, its prevention and management.

Most participants were found to have positive attitude towards prevention of dengue and seeking treatment when they suspect dengue. 44.6% reported that dengue has a cure. 78.3% reported to seek medical care if they suspect dengue and 73.5% had known the benefits of drinking adequate water and taking rest. Nalongsack S et al. also reported that most participants had positive attitude towards visiting doctor when they think they are suffering from dengue infection. The study in contrast to the present study reported less proportion of participants with positive attitude towards drinking much water [16].

In a study by Dhimal M et al., more than 90% participants had reported dengue to be serious illness. The finding was similar to the present study. 93.8% in the present study wanted people to take part actively in vector control activities. Dhimal M et al. also reported a similar proportion of people having positive attitude towards active participation by the community [17].

A study by Afzar M et al. reported most people to have positive attitude with regard to prevention and control of dengue fever [18]. The attitude of the study population is more positive than many other

studies. With regard to practice in the present study, though 81.5% have stated to cover drinking water container in home. About half of the participants were not using mosquito nets to cover windows and doors. Ninety percentages have reported to use anyone mosquito control aids of that most reported it to be mosquito repellent followed by nets. Only a few were using mosquito coils. Only one third reported to have taken part in dengue campaign. 70% reported that they hydrated themselves during the illness which is positive activity to decrease the morbidity due to dengue.

Selvarajoo S et al. in their study reported that some participants were hesitant to remove breeding sites in their own houses which was similar in the present study as only 51% reported to have performed cleaning activities around the house. [11]. Nguyen HV et al. reported very few participants to have practiced activities like covering the water storage container which was not the case in the present study as majority of the participants had reported to have covered drinking water containers [19]. Al-Dubai SAR et al. also reported limited practice towards dengue prevention among the participants [20]. Rahman MM et al. reported majority of their study population to practice behaviours that prevent dengue infection [21].

In the present study though certain practices like covering the drinking water container and utilization of mosquito control aids were on the higher side. Proportion of participants who had reported to have covered the windows and doors with mosquito nets, keeping the containers upside down or cutting the bushes around the house and wearing long sleeve clothing were carried out by only half or lesser of the participants. With regard to the behaviours to be practiced at the time of illness, 70% reported to have hydrated themselves while only 48% reported to have donated blood to a dengue patient.

The strengths of the present study included its objectives only very few studies have been conducted in the study area addressing the above objectives. The knowledge component of the questionnaire has addressed most of the domains could be viewed as another strength. All the practices documented in the study were self-reported practices, direct observation would have estimated it more accurately.

Conclusion

The present study documented good proportion of knowledge among the study participants. Most participants were also found to have positive attitude towards dengue prevention and management activities. Certain practices like source reduction activities and wearing full sleeve

clothing have to be encouraged among the study population.

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